

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Extensification of cultivation practices does not influence plant-parasitic nematode populations

In a field trial during four consecutive growing seasons, an intensive (rotating tillage, intensive fertilization, fallow in between cultivations) and an extensive cropping system (reduced tillage, extensive fertilization, cover crops in between cultivations) were compared and this within both a conventional and an organic cropping system. During this period the crops were leek, celery, cauliflower and roman lettuce. In three out of the four years, nematodes in the soil were sampled by taking composite soil samples of 2 kg from the 0-25 cm soil layer in each cropping system. In each soil sample the nematodes were identified.

In general, no unambiguous effects of the treatment (intensive or extensive soil cultivation) on the amount of plant parasitic nematodes or total amount of nematodes were visible in this

trial. Depending on the species and the cropping cycle, more plant parasitic nematodes of a certain species can occur in either the intensive or the extensive cultivation system. The use of cover crops can increase the amount of plant-parasitic nematodes, whilst the effect on non-plant parasitic nematodes is not distinct.

This trial shows that there is no reason to be afraid of increasing plant-parasitic nematode populations by applying a more extensive cropping system. We did see higher levels of plant-parasitic nematodes in the organic field compared to the conventional field. Cover crop species like *Phacelia tanacetifolia* and *Trifolium incarnatum* can increase plant-parasitic nematode populations.

1. Taking of a composite soil sample to determine the nematode population

2. The number of plant-parasitic and other nematodes for the different treatments throughout the trial years

KEYWORDS

Nematodes, extensive cultivation, cover crops

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